

Latin funerary language: formulae and abbreviations of ancient inscriptions.

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1. Introduction

Identifying formulaic language plays a crucial role in ancient epigraphy, the discipline that aims to study ancient inscriptions. Thousands of texts came down to us from the past inscribed on durable materials such as stones, metal, or pottery. Unfortunately, in many cases, the support on which the text was written was badly damaged over the centuries to the point of illegibility. To fill the gaps in a fragmentary inscription and reconstruct what is lost, epigraphists identify fixed expressions and use them to restore the original text (Woodhead, 1981). This methodology is based on the observation that the language of inscriptions is formulaic. Inscribed texts of similar content share a standardized set of stock word combinations. Enactment formulae in decrees, greetings in letters, and dedications in funerary inscriptions—just to mention a few—are strictly linked to a specific communicative situation while being almost absent in other classes of texts (Ceccarelli, 2018). These various linguistic constructs, encompassing a broad and somewhat undefined category of expressions, are commonly known as *formulae*. They exhibit diversity in length, ranging from single words to entire clauses, and vary in grammatical components and functions.

2. State of the art

Within the domain of ancient Greek and Latin epigraphy, the scholarly debate has revolved around different aspects of formulaicity. Several studies were conducted on the geographic distribution of *formulae* and their variations over time and space. Some studies investigated how formulae spread and the role of human agents in the process of transmission (Adams, 2007: 678–682). Other investigations highlighted that contrary to being mere fillers, standardized expressions carried substantial meaning that mirrored habits, conventions, and ideas (Scafuro, 2013). Moreover, in recent years, a semiotic approach was developed to analyze the interaction of epigraphic *formulae* with the contextual elements of inscriptions such as visual aspect, material, and layout (De la Escosura Balbás et al. 2022).

One of the first attempts to apply a statistical methodology to a corpus of inscriptions was in 1997 when H. Nielsen published an article to quantitatively explore the combination of different *formulae* in Latin funerary texts. More recently, Crellin (2023) extracted multi-word,

not continuous patterns from a syntactically annotated corpus of Latin funerary inscriptions, and Samo et al. (2022) computationally compared the formulaic syntax in tomb inscriptions from Chiusi (Italy) with a larger repository of Latin inscriptions and treebanks. Fantoli & Soffiantini (*forthcoming*) tested a corpus-driven methodology to extract formulaic expressions from two Latin corpora of non-literary texts: Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis Historia* and Latin funerary inscriptions from the Imperial Period. Applying a comparative approach, Fantoli & Soffiantini highlighted that Latin formulae exhibit distinctive features beyond *frequency*, namely *association strength* and *specificity*. From a different perspective, Kaše, Heřmánková, and Sobotková (2021) explored the use of stock word sequences (bigrams) in ancient Latin inscriptions to train a machine-learning model for text classification.

In line with Fantoli & Soffiantini and Kaše, Heřmánková & Sobotková's research, the present paper explores the category of **distinctiveness** as a parameter of **formulaic language**. The purpose of distinctiveness (or *keyness*) analysis is to identify (lexical) items that are typical of a particular text variety (Egbert & Biber, 2019). To achieve this, the paper assesses an adapted version of a commonly used measure of *distinctiveness* using a corpus of ancient inscriptions. The results are discussed qualitatively and then evaluated as a text clustering task. In this way, the paper aims to contribute to the broader debate on the definition of 'epigraphic formula' by underlining the importance of adopting a **comparative approach**.

3. Corpus

For this paper, we used the [Epigraphic Database Roma \(EDR\)](#), a digital corpus of Latin inscriptions coming from Rome and the Italian provinces approximately from the first-century BCE to the fourth century CE (excluding Christian inscriptions). In 2024, the dataset included a total of 108,101 inscriptions openly accessible in XML/TEI format in the [Zenodo](#) archive.

From the EDR corpus, we selected four classes of inscriptions: funerary, votive, honorary, and building inscriptions. Each class corresponds to an interpretative category that labels the primary function of the inscription. The class is assigned following the established domain typologies on the basis of the features of the inscription: the textual content, the context (chronology and geography), and the physical aspect of the material support. In the EDR vocabulary, funerary inscriptions are texts inscribed on tombs; votive inscriptions are dedicated to a deity; honorary inscriptions are texts in honor of someone; and building inscriptions are texts on a building (or similar) affixed by its constructor or restorer.

For this study, we used texts entirely preserved (that is, excluding badly damaged inscriptions). Moreover, to enable the comparison between the classes, the dataset was designed to contain the same number of inscriptions (1,000) by extracting a random sample using the Python *.sample* function in Pandas. The texts are generally quite short, ranging from a mean of 14 tokens per text in funerary and building inscriptions to 31 tokens per text in honorary inscriptions.

In scientific publications, the text of the inscriptions includes special characters and editorial markup indicating integrations (i.e., added letters or words that are no longer readable on the stone), solutions of abbreviations (i.e., expansions of abbreviated words), or larger missing sections in the original text. The pre-processing phase consisted of different steps to clean the texts scraped from EDR and resulted in two text types: in the first one, abbreviations are indicated between round brackets; while in the second one, round brackets were removed. Integrations are always indicated between square brackets. No stemming or lemmatization is performed.

Class	Size (texts)	Size (tokens)	Text length (mean)	Function
Funerary	1,000	14,311	14.311	Written on tomb
Votive	1,000	18,848	18.848	Dedicated to a deity
Honorary	1,000	31,886	31.886	In honor of someone
Building	1,000	14,909	14.909	On buildings, written by the constructor or restorer
	4,000	79,954		

Table 1. Description of the corpus.

4. Methodology

The text classification model for Latin inscriptions proposed in 2021 by Kaše, Heřmánková and Sobotková is based on the Extremely Randomized Trees algorithm (ET) in combination with the Python *sklearn* term frequency-inverse document frequency vectorizer (*Tfidf Vectorizer*). *Tf-idf* is a statistical metric usually utilized in text classification tasks to evaluate the significance of a word's presence in a document within a corpus (Du, Dudar & Schöch, 2022; and see below). The vectorizer assigns different weights to words that are specific to a document and those that are common across the corpus. Instead of individual words, Kaše, Heřmánková and Sobotková opted for bigrams (i.e., two consecutive words), utilizing a vocabulary set comprising the 10,000 most frequent bigrams extracted from the corpus. The authors justify their decision to use bigrams instead of individual words, stating that "Bigrams are suitable to capture the formulaic language of inscriptions" (p. 126). Additionally, the model was trained with metadata, including information about the material of the support on which the inscription was written and a brief description of the textual content.

Their paper primarily focused on the text classification task, with limited attention paid to the implications of the analysis of the inscriptions. For instance, while it's generally noted that bigrams are more suitable for extracting information about word use, the paper lacks a comprehensive theoretical background on this observation. Moreover, the relations between formulaic language analysis, collocation/bigram analysis, and text classification are not thoroughly explored. Furthermore, the results of the *tf-idf* measurement are not qualitatively examined and the paper also does not investigate which aspects of the epigraphic formulaic language the *tf-idf* metrics are capable of quantifying and to what extent these findings can be generalized to other corpora.

What follows aims to address and integrate these open questions through distinctive steps.

- 1) *idf* extraction and analysis
- 2) test-case: bigrams of a dispersed word

(1) As illustrated in Table 2, the *tf-idf* measurement is computed by considering both the relative frequency of a word (t) in a document (d) and the dispersion of t in the corpus (D). In this experiment, we employ the *TfidfVectorizer* from the Python *sklearn* library to calculate and rank the *idf* values of the words in the corpus. The *idf* values represent the logarithmic

ratio between the total size of D and the number of documents in which t occurs, measuring the dispersion of words across the corpus, regardless of their frequency in the documents. In this phase, idf is favored over $tf-idf$ for two reasons. First, idf assigns a unique numeric value to each word in the vocabulary of the corpus, facilitating comparisons between idf values of different words. Like $tf-idf$, low idf values signify highly dispersed words, while higher idf values indicate rarer words. Idf also provides insight into $tf-idf$ values, serving as a kind of 'numeric common base'; the $tf-idf$ of a word in a document depends on the word's frequency and the document's word length, starting from the idf . Secondly, a dispersion measure like idf allows for a quantitative description of a specific feature of inscriptions. Certain words are 'signal words', highly specific to a class of documents, even if they occur only once in each document. In such cases, the $tf-idf$ of the word in a document is the ratio between the idf value and the total number of words in the document.

The idf values are calculated separately for different classes and then for the entire corpus. The purpose of this section is to examine the results obtained by considering different target corpora, thereby elucidating the strengths and limitations of idf .

$$tfidf(t, d, D) = tf(t, d) \cdot idf(t, D)$$

$$tf(t, d) = \frac{f_{t,d}}{\sum_{t' \in d} f_{t',d}}$$

where $f_{t,d}$ is the *raw count* of a term in a document and the denominator is the total number of terms in document d ;

$$idf(t, D) = \log \frac{N}{|\{d \in D : t \in d\}|}$$

where N is the total number of documents in the corpus (D) and the denominator is the number of documents where the term t appears.

Table 2. Description of the $tf-idf$ measure.

(2) In the second part of the paper, we compare two classes of texts. First, we identify the words with the lowest idf values to pinpoint vocabulary that is more dispersed across the texts. This enables us to recognize common themes and topics shared by the two classes. Subsequently, we select a word w from the words with the lowest idf as a test case. We

extract the bigrams of w from each document (d) as follows: using the index i of w in d , we retrieve the bigrams composed by w and each word in a window span of 2 from i , covering words at index positions $i-2$, $i-1$, $i+1$, $i+2$. In this way, the extraction encompasses both consecutive and not-consecutive constructions of the word. For example, given the string: *vivus fecit sibi et suis*, we extract the bigrams *vivus fecit*, *fecit sibi*, *fecit et*. Notably, the notation considers the relative position of the words (*fecit sibi* vs *sibi fecit*) but does not account for the presence of another word between them (*fecit sibi* = *fecit X sibi*). Although this may provide less information about the word sequence, it yields more insightful results in the subsequent step. The *TfidfVectorizer* computes the *tf-idf* matrix of the bigrams that occur in at least three documents (*min_df=3*). Finally, a dimensionality reduction technique (*t-SNE*) in the Python library *plotly.express* is used to visualize the obtained *tf-idf* matrix and examine how texts are clustered solely based on the constructions of a single word.

5. Results

(1) Table 3 ranks the 10 words with the **lowest *idf* values** in funerary, honorary, votive, and building inscriptions, both separately and together. The **most dispersed** words in funerary texts are *manibus* and *dis* usually combined in the funerary opening formula *Dis Manibus*, ‘to the spirits (of the dead)’. This is followed by *vixit*, ‘he/she lived’ often used to indicate the age of death, the function word *et*, ‘and’ and the verb *fecit*, ‘he/she did’ usually referred to the construction the grave. Other **keywords** extracted are the expression *decreto decurionum* ‘by a decree of the *decurioni*’ and *Augusto*, ‘to the Augustus’ indicating the emperor in honorary inscriptions; the words *votum*, ‘vow’, *sacrum* ‘sacred’, *solvit* ‘he/she fulfilled’ and *dedit*, ‘he/she gave’ in votive inscriptions and *fecit*, ‘he/she did’ in building inscriptions.

funerary	honorary	votive	building	ALL
<i>manibus</i> (1.909)	<i>filio</i> (1.945)	<u><i>et</i> (2.457)</u>	<u><i>et</i> (2.510)</u>	<u><i>et</i> (2.303)</u>
<i>dis</i> (1.940)	<u><i>et</i> (2.003)</u>	<i>votum</i> (2.561)	<i>filius</i> (2.556)	<i>filio</i> (3.017)

<i>vixit</i> (2.188)	<i>decurionum</i> (2.387)	<i>sacrum</i> (2.566)	<u><i>fecit</i></u> (2.938)	<u><i>fecit</i></u> (3.150)
<u><i>et</i></u> (2.314)	<i>decreto</i> (2.419)	<i>solvit</i> (2.726)	<i>ex</i> (2.996)	<i>filius</i> (3.156)
<u><i>fecit</i></u> (2.325)	<i>augusto</i> (2.571)	<i>dedit</i> (2.802)	<i>caius</i> (3.010)	<i>manibus</i> (3.278)

Table 3. 10 words with the lowest *idf* values.

The most dispersed word in the entire corpus is *et*, ‘and’, followed by *filio*, ‘to the son’, *fecit* ‘he/she did’, *filius* ‘son’ and *manibus*, ‘to the Manes’. In terms of *specificity*, these words are ranked by *idf* as the **less distinctive**. Notably, the word *et* is present in all the columns. *Filio*, ‘to the son’ appears in the column of honorific inscriptions as the most dispersed word within the class. This word is also dispersed in funerary inscriptions (*idf* = 3.181), and slightly less dispersed in building (*idf* = 5.075) and votive inscriptions (*idf* = 5.136). *Fecit*, ‘he/she did’ is listed both in the columns of funerary and building inscriptions showing similar *idf* values. *Filius* ‘son’ is the second most dispersed word in building inscriptions, and it is quite dispersed also in votive (*idf* = 3.226), funerary (*idf* = 3.454), and honorary (3.797) inscriptions. On the other hand, *manibus* has an *idf* value = 6.810 in honorary inscriptions, while it is not attested in votive and building inscriptions (used in this experiment).

Words with **high *idf* values** are **rarer** and much less dispersed. The highest *idf* values are attributed to words occurring only in one document of the corpus such as rare personal names (*Ladinius*: *idf* = 8.601), but also common nouns (*fondus*: *idf* = 8.601) and verbs (*superest*: *idf* = 8.601). When examining the *idf* values of words **specific** to the class of funerary inscriptions, a broad range of values is observed. For instance, *heredem*, ‘heir’ (*idf* = 7.684), a significant word in funerary texts, is rarer than *monumentum*, ‘monument’ (*idf* = 6.991), *fronte*, ‘(wide) at the front’ (*idf* = 5.487), and *agro* ‘deep’ (*idf* = 5.402) which are used to indicate the dimensions of the burial. The *idf* value these terms are higher than the *idf* of *manibus*, *dis* and *vixit* indicating that they occur in a reduced number of documents, and their presence distinguish those particular documents.

The *idf* measurement quantifies that some words, despite being widely dispersed in a text class, are less distinctive when compared to another class. However, the method has some limitations. While the *idf* measure informs us that a word is more (or less) dispersed in one class than in another, it does not provide information about the significance of the difference. Additionally, retrieving significant words can be challenging due to the wide range of *idf* values. Lastly, it is observed that *idf* is heavily dependent on the balance of the corpus. For instance, the ranking of *manibus* among the 5 most dispersed words might suggest that the word is spread across all four classes of inscriptions, but this conclusion is false. The results of the *idf* extraction need to be contextualized with prior knowledge of the corpus to avoid misleading conclusions.

(2) In the previous section, it was noted that the verb *fecit*, ‘he/she did’ is ranked as one of the most dispersed words both in funerary and building inscriptions. The verb is used in the sense of ‘construct’ and ‘set up’ referring to the construction of the grave in funerary inscriptions and the construction of a building or monument in building inscriptions. This finding is noteworthy as it aligns with the observation that the two classes share other words related to the ‘construction **theme**’ such as the unit of measurement *pedes*, ‘feet’ (building: *idf* = 3.466; funerary: *idf* = 3.901).

To assess to what extent the context of use (i.e. close words) is more specific to a text class than a single word, we inspect the dispersion of the bigrams of *fecit* (Table 4). We find that *fecit* is **used quite differently** and in combination with other words. In funerary inscriptions, the most dispersed bigrams (low *idf*) of *fecit* are in combination with the (preceding) words *merenti* ‘to the deserving’ and *bene* ‘well’ usually used in the expression *bene merenti fecit*, ‘she/he did to the well-deserving’. Other words the verb is used with are *sibi*, ‘to oneself’ and *et*, ‘and’. In building inscriptions, *fecit* is used with *pedes* ‘feet’ in the expression *fecit pedes*, ‘she/he did of feet (dimensions) ...’, and (on the left side of the verb) *sua* ‘their’, *pecunia*, ‘money’, in the expression *sua pecunia fecit*, ‘she/he constructed with their money’, *cum* ‘with’, and *suis* ‘their’ in the expression *cum suis*, ‘with their (relatives)’.

funerary	building
<i>merenti fecit</i> (2.306)	<i>sua fecit</i> (3.328)

<i>bene fecit</i> (2.320)	<i>fecit pedes</i> (3.397)
<i>fecit et</i> (2.799)	<i>pecunia fecit</i> (3.552)
<i>fecit sibi</i> (2.919)	<i>cum fecit</i> (3.957)
<i>fecit vixit</i> (3.750)	<i>suis fecit</i> (3.957)

Table 4. *Idf* values of bigrams of *fecit* in funerary and building inscriptions.

In the scatter plot in Image 1 below, funerary (in red) and building (in blue) inscriptions are **clustered** based on the bigrams of *fecit*. There are four main clusters (surrounded by a green shape). Two clusters on the left contain the funerary texts in which the expressions *bene merenti fecit* and *fecit sibi et* occur. No building inscriptions are present in these clusters. The central larger cluster includes both funerary and building inscriptions in which *fecit* is preceded and/or followed by personal names (i.e., *Calpurnius Lucianus fecit*, *Claudio Proclo fecit Flavia Primitiva*). The cluster on the right encompasses building inscriptions in which the expressions *pecunia sua fecit* or *sua pecunia fecit*, ‘he/she did with their money’ occur.

Other smaller groups consist of building inscriptions containing the expression *fecit pedes*, ‘she/he did of feet (measurement)’ and *cum suis fecit pedes*, ‘with their (relatives) she/he did’. Funerary inscriptions clustered in smaller groups contain the expressions *bene merenti fecit qui vixit*, ‘to the well-deserving she/he did who lived (years)’, *bene merenti fecit vixit* and *fecit vixit annis*, ‘to the well-deserving she/he did. He/she lived years ...’. With the exclusion of the central cluster (see above), funerary and building texts are quite distinct with the exception of cluster of funerary and building inscriptions in which the bigrams *libertus fecit*, ‘the freedperson did’ and *Felix fecit*, ‘Felix did’ occur. Finally, the point indicated by the arrow on the left is blue indicating that it was classified as a building inscription. Its position was peculiar since it is in a region of red points (funerary inscriptions). Upon checking the text, it was revealed that the text ([EDR136211](#)) was misclassified, and it is a funerary inscription as correctly recorded in the corresponding entry in the Trismegistos Database ([TM555768](#)).

Image 1. t-SNE visualization of the *tf-idf* matrix based on *fecit*-bigrams.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we applied the inverse document frequency (*idf*) dispersion measure to a collection of ancient inscriptions to investigate the parameter of *distinctiveness* in the context of formulaic language. When examining a single text class, our observations indicate that formulaic words exhibit low *idf* values (less distinctive), as they are spread across the texts or appear in nearly all of them at least once (keywords). This emphasizes the need to evaluate (epigraphic) formulaicity in terms of dispersion and keyness, rather than relying solely on absolute frequency. While the *idf* measurement has comparative limitations in assessing the significance of word dispersion between different corpora, our findings reveal that similar *idf* values enable the identification of common themes shared among text classes. The analysis of the linguistic context (i.e. close words) specifically through bigram extraction enables us to identify sub-themes and longer formulaic expressions that are more distinctive of a text class compared to individual words.

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